

MDSTs Challenges

Basic Stage Data Collection and Analysis - Interview Questions

General Information: This is an exploratory interview to collect information about the challenges experienced by multi-disciplinary data intensive software teams and how they deal with the challenges.

Research Team:

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No	Round 1 Interview Question (at commencement)	Change	Round 2 Interview Question (After Interview P12)
1	Demographics Where is the location of your work? What is your age? What gender do you identify as? What is the highest qualification you have achieved? What subject area was that qualification in? What is your current role? How many years professional experience do you have? Do you identify as a software engineer, data scientist or domain/business expert or other?	No change	Demographics Where is the location of your work? What is your age? What gender do you identify as? What is the highest qualification you have achieved? What subject area was that qualification in? What is your current role? How many years professional experience do you have? Do you identify as a software engineer, data scientist or domain/business expert or other?
2	Background and current project overview	No change	Please provide a summary of your background and current project overview
3	What are some key characteristics of multidisciplinary teams that deliver data analytics solutions?	No change	What are some key characteristics of multidisciplinary teams that deliver data analytics solutions?
4	What are challenges of working in multi-disciplinary teams that delivery data analytics solutions?	Change prompts to focus on data.	What are challenges of working in multidisciplinary teams? -prompting example, communicating data concepts or data science concepts. -prompting example - have you experienced any challenges relating to communicating data concepts or data science concepts when working in multi-disciplinary teams? Can you share an example? Are there any other challenges?

No	Round 1 Interview Question (at commencement)	Change	Round 2 Interview Question (After Interview P12)
5	What tools and methods does your team use?	Change prompt to focus on data	<p>What data driven/data related tools and processes does your team use to deliver data analytics solutions?</p> <p>Do these tools/processes help improve data quality? How?</p> <p>Do these tools help understanding domain data when delivering data analytics solutions. How?</p>
6	What solution delivery challenges have you experienced when working in a multi-disciplinary team? (Prompt for data quality, support/maintenance, reuse).	Change prompt to focus on data	<p>What solution delivery related challenges have you experienced when delivering <<project>>. Focus on data quality, legacy data, data transformations, features, ability to fix data errors, access to data, data dictionaries etc.</p> <p>What solution delivery challenges do you face when working with data scientists?</p> <p>OR</p> <p>What solution delivery challenges do you face as a data scientist working with software teams?</p>
7	<p>How would you describe your knowledge about software engineering and software engineers?</p> <p>How would you describe your knowledge about the domain/business analysis?</p> <p>How would you describe your knowledge about data science?</p> <p>Etc</p>	Modify questions to focus on the knowledge of the role and technical knowledge about data scientist/data analyst.	<p>If the person is NOT a data scientist/analyst, ask:</p> <p>On a technical, solution delivery level, when working with a data science/data analyst what do you find easy? What is challenging? Why is that?</p> <p>If the person is a data analyst/data scientist, ask:</p> <p>On a technical, solution delivery level, when working with non data scientists, do you find that easy? or what is challenging? Why is that?</p>
8	What human-centric issues have you experienced when delivering solutions?	Modify question	What are your thoughts about how human-centric issues (for example culture, personality, emotional, gender and age) impact how multi-disciplinary teams deliver solutions?
9	What human-centric issues have you catered for in solutions	Drop Question because there has not been a lot of insight from previous interviews in this area. It is not a key concept.	